

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF INTERNET TECHNOLOGY CAPABILITY, INTERNATIONAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP ORIENTATION, INTERNATIONAL NETWORK, AND EXPORT PERFORMANCE OF CREATIVE INDUSTRY SECTOR IN BALI

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Abstract: The purpose of this study is to provide an overview of the capabilities of internet technology, international entrepreneurial orientation, international networks and export performance achievements of creative industry SMEs in Bali. The population of this research is creative industry SMEs that have exported in Bali. The size of the sample used is 170 managers / owners of creative industry SMEs with purposive sampling method. The analysis technique used is descriptive analysis. The results of the study indicate that the capability of internet technology and international entrepreneurial orientation possessed by creative industry SMEs in Bali is quite high. Its international network is in good category, and its export performance is quite good. Therefore, it is important for creative industry SMEs in Bali to continue to improve their internet technology capabilities and international entrepreneurial orientation to a higher level, which is very high, so that their international network becomes very high and the achievement of export performance is high or very high. Things that need to be done include: improving its internet technology infrastructure, communicating its successful mission in international markets more often, increasing resources to support activities in international markets, and attaching importance to encouragement to enter international markets.

Keywords: internet technology capability, international entrepreneurial orientation, international network, export performance, creative industry.

1. INTRODUCTION

SMEs are one of the backbones of a country's economy. Therefore, the government always tries to empower existing SMEs to keep growing. One of the reliable SMEs in Bali Province is the creative industry sector SMEs. This is because SMEs in the creative industry sector have worked on local and foreign (export) markets. This provides an opportunity for SMEs to gain a wider market and higher marketing performance. To achieve this export performance, of course, SMEs in the creative industry sector must be smart in managing their resources. One of the basic resources used in order to carry out an export strategy is the strategy of using internet technology to market their products (Sinkovics et al., 2013; Eduarksen, 2018;

Samiee, 2020; Zhong et al., 2020). Internet technology resources are related to the capabilities that must be owned by an SME. By having high internet technology capabilities, the achievement of export performance can increase. The results of this kind of research are shown by several researchers, namely: Bianchi et al. (2017); Wang and Tao (2019); Mahmoud et al. (2020); Liu et al. (2020); Wang (2020); Rauf et al. (2021); Cassia and Magno (2022).

In addition to relying on internet technology capabilities, creative industry SMEs in Bali always try to be creative and innovate that reflects their entrepreneurial orientation to support increasing export performance. The influence of entrepreneurial orientation, especially international entrepreneurial orientation on export performance, has been carried out by several researchers, namely: Jin and Cho (2018); Baldegger et al. (2021); Mostafiz et al. (2021); Dung and Giang (2021); Faroque et al. (2021); Crick and Crick (2022), which shows that the higher the international entrepreneurial orientation, the higher the export performance. Likewise, export performance will be even higher if it is supported by international network access. This is revealed in the results of research from several previous researchers, namely: Kenny and Fahy (2011); Pham et al. (2017); Hasaballah et al. (2019); Wang (2020); Malca et al. (2021); Chang and Huang (2022), which states that if the international network of a company is wider, the achievement of its business performance will also increase. The three variables that determine export performance can be used as the basis for developing business strategies in order to improve export performance.

Based on the background of the existing problems, the purpose of this research is to provide an overview of the capabilities of internet technology, entrepreneurial orientation, and international networks, as well as the export performance of the creative industry sector SMEs in Bali and to formulate strategies to improve their export performance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Internet Technology Capability

According to Bianchi et al. (2017), internet technology capabilities are intangible resources that give rise to knowledge, analytical processes to turn information technology into value for the company. Through the capabilities of internet technology, SMEs can reach a wider market to foreign countries. This is because with the internet, improving the quality and speed of communication and transactions, and decreasing costs, these advances have made internationalization more feasible for SMEs with limited resources.

The Internet also has the capacity to enhance learning about international markets through faster and wider access to relevant information (Mathews et al., 2021), and assists in the development of international networks (Bianchi et al., 2017). Overall, internet capabilities can increase the ability of SMEs to transform processes into business activities that support international market performance (Shehata and Montash, 2020). In summary, this study aims to contribute by extending the theory of the Resources Based View (Barney, 2001) and empirically examining the effect of Internet technology capabilities, entrepreneurial orientation, and their impact on international networking and international performance for SMEs in Bali.

Internet technology capabilities are often referred to as information technology capabilities or digital technology capabilities. All of these have a positive influence in building wider relationships with stakeholders, both buyers, suppliers, and partners abroad. Research conducted by Bianchi et al. (2017) states that internet technology capability consists of several measurements such as: seen from the investment of SMEs in information technology, their information technology capabilities, technology infrastructure support, and involvement in e-commerce competencies.

International Entrepreneurship Orientation

The concept of entrepreneurial orientation has extended to the international market environment. Entrepreneurial orientation is seen as a dynamic ability that has a tendency to sense and capture international opportunities in an innovative, market-oriented, and timely manner. Entrepreneurial orientation is an orientation to seize international opportunities, taking these opportunities into their market share (Gull et al., 2021). Entrepreneurial orientation in the international market environment greatly determines the company's ability to build networks and improve performance, including export performance. Entrepreneurial orientation is measured from the company's view that it considers the world as a market that needs to be worked on, seeks new business opportunities in the international market, dares to convey its mission to succeed in international markets, always develops resources to support entry into international markets, and emphasizes the driving factors for entry into the international market. international market (Bianchi et al., 2017; Mathews et al., 2021).

International Network

Andersson et al. (2018), said that international networks are the company's relationship with stakeholders abroad. Jeong et al. (2019) and Freund et al. (2020), said that international networks would really help companies in communicating their products to the market and also getting information on raw materials from suppliers in the international market. Likewise, according to Ahimbisibwe et al. (2020), international networks make it easier for companies to build relationships with customers, suppliers and partners that are abroad.

In this study, international networking was measured from: the company's ability to use the internet to maintain relationships with international customers, use the internet to strengthen existing international relationships, use the internet to acquire new international customers, use the internet to enter new international market countries, and use the internet. to improve the company's international performance (Bianchi et al., 2017).

Export Performance

The success of SMEs in the international market is highly dependent on the company's ability to change and adapt to new developments, such as development applications and internet infrastructure, the entrepreneurial mindset of business people, and the networking capabilities of the company. International performance or often referred to as export performance for SMEs is performance with a multi-dimensional construct that combines various dimensions of company performance, such as financial and non-financial performance (Sukaatmadja et al., 2021). In this study, the measurement of export performance will use these two dimensions, consisting of: international market share achievement, sales turnover growth performance, profit growth, and managers' perceptions of satisfaction with their international activities (Bianchi et al., 2017; Mathews et al., 2021).

3. RESEARCH METHODS

When viewed from the nature of the problem, this research is a descriptive type of research. That is, this study provides an overview of respondents' perceptions of internet technology capabilities, international entrepreneurial orientation, international networks, and export performance. This research was conducted on managers or owners of creative industry SMEs in the Province of Bali who have already exported. The data collected as many as 30 respondents were tested for validity and reliability. The results of the validity and reliability tests show that the correlation values of all indicators are all above 0.30; and the results of the reliability test showed the results of the Cronbach's Alpha value of all variables above 0.6. Furthermore, data collection was continued by distributing questionnaires to 170 managers or owners of creative industry SMEs in Bali. A sample of 170 respondents, then analyzed using analytical tools, namely: descriptive analysis.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Testing the validity and reliability of the instrument was carried out with the Pearson Correlation and the Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient. As has been stated, the research instrument is called valid if the Pearson Product Moment correlation value r 0.30 and reliable if the Cronbach's Alpha value 0.60. The test results on thirty (30) respondents have been carried out and give the results as presented in Table I.

TABLE I. INSTRUMENT VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY TEST RESULTS

Variable	Item	r correlation	Cronbach's Alpha α
Internet Technology Capability (X1)	X1		0,922
	X1.1	0,946	
	X1.2	0,927	
	X1.3	0,920	
International Entrepreneurship Orientation (X2)	Y1		0,934
	Y1.1	0,853	
	Y1.2	0,891	
	Y1.3	0,888	
	Y1.4	0,883	
	Y1.5	0,950	
International Network (Y1)	Y2		0,887
	Y2.1	0,880	
	Y2.2	0,853	
	Y2.3	0,887	
	Y2.4	0,792	

	Y2.5	0,730	
Export Performance (Y2)	Y3		0,906
	Y3.1	0,940	
	Y3.2	0,876	
	Y3.3	0,859	
	Y3.4	0,831	

Source: processed data, 2023

Description of Respondent Characteristics

The characteristics of the respondents in this study were seen from gender, age, education, position, number of workers, and length of establishment of the business. The composition of the characteristics of research respondents is presented in Table II.

TABLE II. CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

No	Variable	Classification	Total	Percentage (%)
1	Gender	Man	95	55,88
		Woman	75	44,12
		Total	170	100,00
2	Age	20 - 30	5	2,94
		>30 - 40	25	14,71
		>40 - 50	45	26,47
		>50 - 60	80	47,06
		>60	15	8,82
	Total	170	100,00	
3	Education level	Highschool	44	25,88
		Diploma	13	7,65
		Undergraduate	86	50,59
		Postgraduate	27	15,88
		Total	170	100,00
4	Position	Manager	76	44,71
		Owner	94	55,29
		Total	170	100,00
5	Number of workers	5 - 10	5	2,94
		11 - 20	10	5,88
		21 - 40	80	47,06
		41 - 100	75	44,12
		Total	170	100,00
6	Length of establishment	2 – 5 years	15	8,82
		>5 – 10 years	35	20,59
		>10 years	120	70,59
		Total	170	100,00

Source: processed data, 2023

Table II provides an overview of the profiles of 170 respondents which are presented in general with several characteristics including gender, age, education, position, number of workers, length of establishment of the company. The characteristics of the respondents in this study can be described as follows. There are more male respondents than female respondents, namely 95 male respondents and 75 female respondents. Age ranges from 20 years to 65 years, with the following distribution are 5 people aged 20-30 years, 25 people > 30-40 years old, 45 people > 40-50 years old, 80 people > 50-60 years old, and 15 people > 60 years old. The education level of the respondents is as follows: 44 high school students, 13 Diploma students, 86 undergraduate students, and 27 postgraduate students. The position of the respondent is more owner and manager as many as 94 people and the manager as many as 74 people. The number of SME workers who became respondents were as follows: the number of workers of 5-10 people was 5, the number of workers of 11-20 people was 10

SMEs, with the number of workers 21-40 people were 80 SMEs, and the number of workers was 41 - 100 people as many as 75 SMEs. Furthermore, for the length of establishment of the business, 15 SMEs have been established for 2 – 5 years, > 5 – 10 years are 35 SMEs, and > 10 years are 120 SMEs.

Descriptive Statistical Analysis

The frequency distribution is obtained from the score of respondents' answers. The interpretation of item scores in research variables can be seen in Table III below.

The description of the descriptive statistical analysis of each variable, as follows:

TABLE III. MEASUREMENT CRITERIA DESCRIPTION OF RESEARCH VARIABLES

No.	Measurement Scale	Internet technology capability , International entrepreneurial orientation, export performance	International Network
1	1,00 – 1,80	Very low	Very bad
2	> 1,80 – 2,60	Low	Bad
3	> 2,60 – 3,40	High enough	Pretty good
4	> 3,40 – 4,20	Hugh	Good
5	> 4,20 – 5,00	Very high	Very good

Internet Technology Capability (X1)

Internet technology capability variable is one of the variables related to international network variables and export performance. This research variable measures the internet technology capabilities of creative industry SMEs in Bali with a quantitative approach, which is based on the responses of respondents (students) to the indicators of internet technology capabilities owned by creative industry SMEs in Bali, namely the indicator: investment in internet technology (X1.1); information technology capability (X1.2); and technology infrastructure, (X1.3). Respondents' perceptions of the internet technology capability variable can be seen in Table IV.

TABLE IV. RESULTS OF DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF INTERNET TECHNOLOGY CAPABILITY VARIABLES (X1)

Indicator	Score					Mean	Description
	1	2	3	4	5		
Invest in internet technology (X1.1)	7	29	27	65	42	3,62	High
Information technology capability (X1.2)	8	30	19	54	59	3,74	High
Information technology infrastructure (X1.3)	5	46	47	39	33	3,29	Pretty high
Internet Technology Capability						3,55	High

Source: processed data, 2023

Internet technology capability owned by creative industry SMEs in Bali is shown by variable indicators of internet technology capability owned by creative industry SMEs in Bali, namely: investment in internet technology (X1.1); information technology capability (X1.2); technology infrastructure, (X1.3). Based on Table IV, it can be seen that of the 170 respondents studied, it turns out that in general the perception of creative industry SME managers in Bali on the variable indicators of internet technology capability has an average score of 3.55 and it is stated that the internet technology capabilities they have are high. This illustrates a condition that the respondent understands the capabilities of internet technology as indicated by technology investment which results in greater international sales, information technology capabilities, and technology infrastructure.

Of the three indicators of internet technology capability, it turns out that the indicator of information technology capability shows the highest mean value, which is 3.74, while the lowest is information technology infrastructure with a mean value of 3.29. This illustrates that according to the creative industry SME managers in Bali that information technology infrastructure must be improved again.

International Entrepreneurship Orientation (X2)

Measurement of the international entrepreneurial orientation of creative industry SMEs in Bali, refers to the research of Bianchi et al. (2017) which consists of: the company views the world as a market (X2.1), pursues new international business opportunities (X2.2), communicates its mission of success in international markets (X2.3), develops resources for goals in international markets (X2.4), and emphasize the impetus to enter the international market (X2.5).

Based on Table V, it can be seen that of the 170 respondents studied, it turns out that in general the perception of creative industry SME managers in Bali towards the international entrepreneurial orientation variable indicator is in the high category with an average score of 3.54. This illustrates a condition that respondents understand the international entrepreneurial orientation shown by the company views the world as a market, pursues new international business opportunities, communicates its mission to succeed in international markets, develops resources for goals in international markets, and attaches importance to encouragement to enter international markets is high.

TABLE V. RESULTS OF DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF INTERNATIONAL ENTREPRENEURIAL ORIENTATION VARIABLES (X2)

Indicator	Score					Mean	Description
	1	2	3	4	5		
The company views the world as a market (X2.1)	10	35	19	52	54	3,62	High
Pursuing new international business opportunities, (X2.2)	6	42	24	44	54	3,58	High
Communicates its mission of success in international markets (X2.3)	6	46	38	39	41	3,37	Pretty High
Develop resources for goals in international markets (X2.4)	8	31	31	56	44	3,57	Pretty High
Emphasize push to enter international market (X2.5)	8	32	27	59	44	3,58	Pretty High
International Entrepreneurial Orientation						3,54	High

Source: Data processed, 2023

Of the five types of international entrepreneurship orientation indicators, it turns out that the indicator value views the world as a market (X2.1), showing the highest mean value of 3.62 while the lowest is an indicator of communicating its mission to success in the international market (X2.3), which is 3.37. This illustrates that creative industry SME managers in Bali have a view of assuming the global world as a high target market for their products, while the indicators of communicating a successful mission in the international market to all company employees need to be improved, for example by providing attractive rewards if successful in the international market.

International Network (Y1)

The international network variable in this study measures with a quantitative approach, which is based on the responses of the creative industry SME managers in Bali to the international networking indicators, namely indicators of internet use to retain international customers (Y1.1), internet use to strengthen relationships with international customers. (Y1.2), acquiring new international customers, (Y1.3), entering new international market countries (Y1.4), using the internet to improve the company's international performance (Y1.5).

Respondents' perceptions of the attitude variable can be seen in Table VI.

TABLE VI. RESULTS OF DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF INTERNATIONAL NETWORK VARIABLES (Y1)

Source: Data processed, 2023

Indicator	Score					Mean	Description
	1	2	3	4	5		
Internet use to retain international customers (Y1.1)	7	28	59	43	33	3,39	Pretty good
Use of the internet to strengthen relationships with international customers (Y1.2)	2	29	43	53	43	3,62	Good
Acquired new international customers (Y1.3)	2	18	56	53	41	3,66	Good
Entering new international market countries (Y1.4)	2	29	40	56	43	3,64	Good
Use of the internet to improve the company's international performance (Y1.5).	2	16	56	56	40	3,68	Good
International Network						3,60	Good

International networks are indicated by indicators of using the internet to retain international customers (Y1.1), using the internet to strengthen relationships with international customers (Y1.2), acquiring new international customers, (Y1.3), entering into new international market countries (Y1.4), the use of the internet to improve the company's international performance (Y1.5). Based on Table 6, it can be seen that from 170 respondents studied, in general the perception of creative industry SME managers in Bali on international networking variables is in the good category with an average score of 3.60. This illustrates a condition that the respondent has a good international network with international stakeholders.

Of the five international network indicators, it turns out that the internet usage indicator for international performance improvement shows the highest mean value, which is 3.68, while the lowest is the use of the internet to retain customers with a mean value of 3.39. This means that creative industry SMEs need to continue to increase their use of the internet to retain customers.

Export Performance (Y2)

The measurement of the export performance of creative industry SMEs in Bali consists of: international market share performance (Y2.1), international sales growth performance (Y2.2), international profit (XY.3); and satisfaction about its international activities (Y1.4). Based on Table VII, it can be seen that of the 170 respondents studied, it turns out that in general the perception of creative industry SME managers in Bali on the indicators of export performance variables is in the very high category with an average score of 3.16. This illustrates a condition that respondents understand about the achievement of export performance as indicated by indicators of international market share, international sales growth performance, international profits; and satisfaction about its international activities.

TABLE VII. RESULTS OF DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF EXPORT PERFORMANCE VARIABLES (Y2)

Indicator	Score					Mean	Description
	1	2	3	4	5		
International market share growth (Y2.1)	33	49	36	29	23	2,76	Pretty high
International sales growth (Y2.2)	12	54	49	25	30	3,04	Pretty high
Increased international profits (Y2.3)	5	9	67	47	42	3,66	High
Satisfaction with international activities (Y2.4)	4	15	66	45	40	3,60	High
Export Performance						3,16	Pretty high

Source: Data processed, 2023

Of the four types of export performance indicators, it turns out that the value of the increasing international profit indicator (Y2.3) shows the highest mean value, which is 3.66, while the lowest is the international market share growth indicator (Y2.1), which is 2.76. This illustrates that the export performance of creative industry SMEs in Bali is quite high, while the international market share growth performance indicators need to be continuously improved.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS OF THE RESEARCH

Based on the results of the descriptive analysis, it can be concluded that the internet technology capability owned by the creative industry exporter SMEs in Bali is rated on average in the high rating range, which consists of high internet technology investment, high information technology capability, and quite high information technology infrastructure. For the level of international entrepreneurial orientation of creative industry SMEs in Bali is also rated high, this means that international entrepreneurial orientation is good but can still be improved to be very high, as well as the international network of creative industry SMEs in Bali is good, but there is one indicator variable namely the use of the internet to retain existing customers is still in the fairly good category. Furthermore, the achievement of export performance received a fairly high assessment. In the future, this needs to be improved again so that export performance will be high. For this reason, in the future, to increase international networking and export performance of creative industry SMEs in Bali, it is necessary to add other variables such as the need to do digital marketing, maintain quality relationships with customers and suppliers.

This research can provide an overview of the capabilities of internet technology, international entrepreneurial orientation, international networks, and export performance achievements of creative industry SMEs in Bali, so that the research results can be used as the basis for formulating a strategy model for increasing export performance for creative industry SMEs in Bali based on technology capabilities. internet and international entrepreneurial orientation.

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